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CONNECTING SCIENCE WITH SOCIETY

Deliverable No. 4.7

Awareness sessions at First Town Hall Meeting

Submission of Deliverable

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Introduction

WP4 is creating the framework to enable all other WPs to integrate stakeholder engagement within their objectives and tasks and is therefore closely connected to them. A key aim for WP4 is to add value by making optimal use of established networks, professional tools, methods, expertise and skills to strengthen and broaden existing stakeholder interactions and create new opportunities for raising awareness, promoting a constructive dialogue, and generating measurable impact from the EU-PolarNet research programme.

The Town hall event that was held on September 27th 2016 in Brussels was an important tool in raising awareness amongst stakeholders on ways to get involved in the EU-PolarNet project.

Awareness sessions

International partners and stakeholders are already or will be involved in all phases of EU-PolarNet. They are also part of the project management structure as members of the External Expert Advisory Board and guests in the General Assembly. EU-PolarNet conducted a very detailed stakeholder mapping and is now in the phase of identifying their needs. This will include many awareness-raising events in which EU-PolarNet will stress that it will consider the input of these groups seriously. The programme of the Town Hall event was compiled in such a way that it can be considered as an important awareness session. The objective of the meeting was to stimulate a dialogue between international and national policy makers, polar scientists, industries, local communities and civil society to explore how future polar research can contribute to the “1.5°C target” agreed at the Paris COP21 meeting last year. It also gave the science community and other stakeholders a wider introduction to the ambitions of the strategic framework and implementation plan. Close to 1000 people were invited to this meeting and more than 20 international press contacts received a press release.

The meeting was well attended by 110 people from industry, policy, NGOs and science. A live video stream was set up to allow more people to follow the presentations at the Town hall event. At least 180 people have watched (at least parts) of the morning session online and more than 125 the afternoon session since. Furthermore a Storify was created on Twitter, compiling all tweets that were related to the Town hall event and enabling people attending the event via live stream to pose questions and comments using the hash tag #EUpolarpriorities.

Questionnaire

In order to get more information from the stakeholders that attended the Town hall meeting a questionnaire was developed and handed out during the meeting. The questionnaire sought to find out what motivates stakeholders to engage in polar projects, as well as the extent and the way they would like to get involved in future projects. The main objective of the questionnaire was to facilitate initial science-stakeholder dialogues, as well as to manage expectations and identify needs from the onset of a partnership. Fifteen participants filled in this questionnaire. A week later, at the Arctic Circle conference in Reykjavik, the questionnaire was also handed out during the well-attended session that EU-PolarNet and ICE-Arc were co-organising. This resulted in seventeen more questionnaires. It is positive to note that most respondents gave their contact details and were interested in getting engaged in various stages of research projects.